

Polarographic study of stability constant and thermodynamic parameters of [Mn-L-amino acidate-vitamin-PP] system vis-à-vis electrode kinetics

Farid Khan* and Kavita Rai

Electrochemical Laboratory, Department of Chemistry, Dr. H. S. Gour University, Sagar-470 003, Madhya Pradesh, India

E-mail : faridkhan58@yahoo.com, farid.fk@reddifmail.com

Manuscript received 6 August 2009, revised 18 February 2010, accepted 25 February 2010

Abstract : The polarographic behavior of complexes of Mn^{II} with glycine, α -alanine, L-leucine, L-valine, L-asparagine and L-glutamine as primary ligands and vitamin-PP (nicotinamide) as secondary ligand was studied using manual polarography at $pH = 7.30 \pm 0.01$, $\mu = 1.0 M NaClO_4$ at $25^\circ C$ and $35^\circ C$. Mn^{II} formed 1 : 1 : 1, 1 : 1 : 2 and 1 : 2 : 1 complexes with these ligands as confirmed by Schaap and McMaster method. The sequence of the stability constant of complexes was L-glutamine < L-asparagine < L-valine < L-leucine < α -alanine < glycine, log of which varied from 1.68 to 9.45. The kinetic parameters are determined using Tamamushi and Tanaka method. The transfer coefficient (α) varied from 0.40 to 0.55 (0.50) confirmed that transition state behaves between reactant and product response to applied potential and it lies always between dropping mercury electrode and solution interface. The waves were characterized as being quasireversible with diffusion controlled. The thermodynamic parameters enthalpy change (ΔH), free energy change (ΔG) and entropy change (ΔS) also determined.

Keywords : Vitamin-PP, Mn^{II} , L-amino acids, kinetics, stability constant.

Introduction

Amino acids are key structural element of the peptides and other natural products. In addition, they are essential building blocks for the synthesis of pharmaceutically active compounds¹. They also take part in the intracellular metabolism and operate specific transport system of the plasma membrane without affecting the cardiac function under normal conditions². Vitamin-PP (nicotinamide) is a coenzyme which takes part in many biological oxidation-reduction reactions³. In addition, nitrogen-containing ligands may be used in catalysis with transition metals⁴.

Mn^{II} is essential for the normal bone formation, enzyme functions and amino acids metabolism⁵. The complexation of manganese with amino acids and vitamin-PP may be an important determinant role in toxicodynamics and neurotoxicity⁶. Therefore, the complexes of Mn with amino acids and vitamin-PP have great importance.

Results and discussion

Mn^{II} showed two electron quasireversible reduction wave at $pH = 7.30 \pm 0.01$ and $\mu = 1.0 M NaClO_4$ at $25^\circ C$ and $35^\circ C$ ⁷.

The nature of current-voltage curve for complexes is also quasireversible. The concentrations of Mn^{II} , $NaClO_4$ and Triton X-100 (as suppressor) in the test solution were 0.5 mM, 1.0 M and 0.001% respectively. In [Mn-L-amino acids-vitamin-PP] system, the concentration of primary ligands i.e. L-amino acids varied from 0.5 to 30.0 mM at 0.025 M and 0.050 M fixed concentration of secondary ligand (vitamin-PP). The $E_{1/2}$ became more negative with the addition of vitamin-PP to the [Mn-L-amino acids] system which showed ternary complex formation of 1 : 1 : 1, 1 : 1 : 2 and 1 : 2 : 1 complexes. Gellings⁸ method was used to determine the values of $E_{1/2}^r$ from $E_{1/2}^{qr}$ value by plotting $[E - RT/nF \log (i_d - i)/i]$ vs i for all the complexes. The data and plots of $F_{ij} [X, Y]$ against $[X]$ (where F_{ij} is a Schaap and McMaster⁹ function to evaluate the stability constant β_{ij} , X = glycine, Y = vitamin-PP and i and j are their stoichiometric numbers respectively) for [Mn-glycine-vitamin-PP] system were shown in Fig. 1 which is used to determine the values of function F_{00} , F_{10} , F_{20} and F_{30} and also to calculate the stability constant given in Table 1.

Fig. 1. Plot of $F_{ij}[X, Y]$ vs $[X]$ for [Mn-glycine-vitamin-PP] system.

change (ΔH), free energy change (ΔG) and entropy change (ΔS) are given in Table 2. These values showed that the complexes are not stable at higher temperature^{12,13}. The negative values of (ΔH) ensure that the reactions are exothermic in nature.

The stability of the binary and ternary complexes compared with the $\log K$ values calculated by the following equation⁹.

$$\log K_m = \log \beta_{11} - 1/2 [\log \beta_{02} + \log \beta_{20}]$$

The values of $\log K_m$ were $-0.071, -0.105, -0.167, 0.616, 0.577$ and 0.569 respectively for [Mn-glycinate-vitamin-PP], [Mn- α -alaninate-vitamin-PP], [Mn-L-leucinate-vitamin-PP], [Mn-L-valinate-vitamin-PP], [Mn-L-asparaginate-vitamin-PP] and [Mn-L-glutaminat-vitamin-PP] systems respectively.

The positive values of $\log K_m$ indicated that the ternary complexes are more stable than the corresponding binary complexes, whereas the negative values indicated that the binary complexes are more stable than their corresponding ternary complexes.

The sequence of the stability constant of the com-

Table 1. Stability constants of [Mn-L-amino acids-vitamin-PP] system

Ligands	$\log \beta_{01}$	$\log \beta_{02}$	$\log \beta_{10}$	$\log \beta_{20}$	$\log \beta_{30}$	$\log \beta_{11}$	$\log \beta_{12}$	$\log \beta_{21}$
Glycine	-	-	4.20	7.10	9.30	4.40	7.85	9.45
L-Alanine	-	-	4.13	7.03	9.23	4.30	7.15	9.35
L-Leucine	-	-	4.10	7.00	9.10	4.18	-	9.15
L-Valine	-	-	4.03	-	9.03	4.13	7.00	9.10
L-Asparagine	-	-	3.98	6.91	-	4.05	6.95	-
L-Glutamine	-	-	6.84	6.84	8.88	3.98	6.90	9.00
Vitamin-PP	1.68	2.63	-	-	-	-	-	-

The cathodic wave for Mn^{II} and its complexes were quasireversible as confirmed by kinetic parameters and slopes of current-voltage data. For other systems, the waves were also quasireversible. The kinetic parameters of the complexes viz. transfer coefficient (α), degree of irreversibility (λ) and rate constant (k) were determined by Tamamushi and Tanaka methods^{10,11}. The parameter Z , which is measure of the degree of irreversibility, has been calculated by the equation given in the literature^{10,11}.

The values of thermodynamic parameters viz. enthalpy

plexes was L-glutamine < L-asparagine < L-valine < L-leucine < α -alanine < glycine which can be explained on the basis of basicities and structures of the primary ligands¹⁴.

In case of Mn^{II} complexes, L-amino acids coordinate through the amino nitrogen and oxygen of COOH group¹⁵ and vitamin-PP coordinates through the N-atom of the pyridine ring with metal ion. The glycine formed the complexes of maximum stability and L-glutamine formed complexes of minimum stability with Mn^{II} metal ion. The

Table 2. Thermodynamic parameters of [Mn-L-amino acids-vitamin-PP] ternary complexes

Systems	Stability constants				-ΔH (kcal/mol)				-ΔG (kcal/mol)				-ΔS (kcal/mol)				
	log β ₁₁	log β ₁₂	log β ₂₁	β ₁₁	log β ₁₂	log β ₂₁	log β ₁₂	log β ₂₁	β ₁₁	log β ₁₂	log β ₂₁	log β ₁₂	log β ₂₁	β ₁₁	log β ₁₂	log β ₂₁	
	25 °C/ 35 °C	25 °C/ 35 °C	25 °C/ 35 °C	(35 °C-25 °C)	for difference of 10 °C	for difference of 10 °C	25 °C/ 35 °C	25 °C/ 35 °C	25 °C/ 35 °C	25 °C/ 35 °C	25 °C/ 35 °C	25 °C/ 35 °C	25 °C/ 35 °C	25 °C/ 35 °C	25 °C/ 35 °C	25 °C/ 35 °C	
[Mn-glycinate-vitamin-PP]	4.40	7.85	9.45	16.8004	14.7003	18.9004	6.0001	10.7047	12.8865	36.2426	13.4081	20.1807	20.1813	17.1776	17.1795	15.4989	15.5006
[Mn-α-alaninate-vitamin-PP]	4.30	7.15	9.35	14.7000	16.3804	17.2204	5.8637	9.7502	12.7502	14.6807	16.3477	17.1776	17.1776	17.1795	15.4989	15.5006	13.3986
[Mn-L-leucinate-vitamin-PP]	4.18	-	9.15	15.9604	-	15.5404	5.7001	-	12.3411	15.9412	-	15.4989	15.5006	13.3986	13.4001	-	-
[Mn-L-valinate-vitamin-PP]	4.13	7.00	9.10	15.5404	18.9000	13.4403	5.6319	9.5456	12.4093	15.5215	18.8684	13.3986	13.4001	13.4001	13.4001	13.4001	13.4001
[Mn-L-asparaginate-vitamin-PP]	4.05	6.95	-	14.7003	18.0604	-	5.5228	9.4774	-	14.6818	18.0286	-	-	-	-	-	-
[Mn-L-glutaminatinate-vitamin-PP]	3.98	6.90	9.00	17.6404	15.9604	17.6404	5.4274	9.4092	12.2729	17.6222	15.9288	17.5992	17.5992	17.5992	17.5992	17.5992	17.5992
							5.0175	9.1893	12.0926	17.6241	15.9305	17.6011	17.6011	17.6011	17.6011	17.6011	17.6011

Note

stability of complexes decreases with the increase in the bulk of the side chain of primary ligands². The values of stability constant (log β) varied from 1.68 to 9.45¹⁶.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AR grade and their solutions were prepared in conductivity water. The concentrations of Mn^{II} and L-amino acids were taken in the ratio of 1 : 40 : 40 and current-voltage curves were obtained at the different pH range from 7.10 to 8.50, but pH 7.30 ± 0.01 was selected on account of studying the complexes in human blood pH. Elico-pH Meter (Model LI-120) was used to measure the pH of the analyte at 7.30 ± 0.01 adjusted with dilute solutions of NaOH or HClO₄ as required. Potassium dihydrogen phosphate buffer was added to stabilize the pH of the analyte. The current-voltage curves were recorded on a manual polarograph using polyflex galvanometer (PL-50). The polarographic cell was of Laitinen and Lingane¹⁷ type in which capillary of 5.0 cm in length with 0.04 mm in diameter was used. The $m^{2/3} t^{1/6}$ value was 2.40 mg^{2/3} s^{1/2} at 60.02 cm effective height of mercury.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Head, Department of Chemistry, Dr. H. S. Gour University, Sagar, for providing the laboratory facilities.

References

1. Von Nubaum, F. Spiteller and P. Highlights, in "Bioinorganic Chemistry, Methods and Applications", eds. C. Schmuck and H. Wennemers, Wiley-VCH, Weinheim, 2004, 63.
2. F. Khan and A. Khanam, *Portugal. Electrochim. Acta*, 2009, 27, 87.
3. H. Sund, "Pyridine Nucleotide-dependent Dehydrogenases", W. de Gruyter & Co., Berlin, Germany, 1977.
4. M. J. Alcon, M. Iglesias, F. Sánchez and I. Viani, *J. Organomet. Chem.*, 2000, 601, 284.
5. M. L. Scott, M. C. Nesheim and R. J. Young, "Nutrition of Chicken", M. L. Scott of Ithika, New York, 1976.
6. A. C. Chua and E. H. Morgan, *J. Comp. Physio.*, 1997, B-167, 361.
7. F. Khan and Rakhi Agrawal, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2008, 86, 83.
8. P. J. Gellings, *Z. Electrochem. Ber. Bunsenges Phys. Chem.*, 1962, 66, 481; 1963, 67, 167.
9. W. B. Schaap and D. L. McMaster, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 83, 4699.
10. R. Tamamushi and N. Tanaka, *Z. Phys. Chem., Neue Folge*, 1963, 39, 117.
11. R. Tamamushi, K. Ishibashi and N. Tanaka, *Z. Phys. Chem., Neue Folge*, 1962, 35, 211.
12. F. Khan and A. Khanam, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2008, 85, 89.
13. F. Khan and A. Zaidi, *J. Inst. Chem. (India)*, 2000, 72, 104.
14. J. D. Joshi, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1984, 61, 901.
15. R. Pabitra, P. K. Bhattacharya and Neely Emanuel, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1985, 62, 940.
16. M. D. Walker and D. L. Williams, *J. Chem. Soc. (Dalton)*, 1974, 1186.
17. L. Meites, "Polarographic Technique", 2nd ed., Interscience Publishers, New York, 1965.